

OPPORTUNITIES TO USE NATIONAL HERITAGE THROUGH EDUCATION LESSONS FOR PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract

In this article, the possibilities of using national heritage through educational lessons for elementary school students are contained in the well-defined laws of the educational content, which have been improved over the centuries in accordance with the requirements of each era. In the content of education, the knowledge, skills and abilities, personal behavior and moral qualities that must be used from the heritage of our ancestors are embodied in accordance with the educational goals and tasks set according to the age and social origin of the student.

Key words: moral standards, humanity, modesty, mutual help, love, kindness, support of justice, humanitarianism, hatred of immorality, understanding of the essence, education, manners, high culture.

It is known that pedagogical technology was introduced in many developed countries in the middle of the 20th century. In the last quarter of the century, it has become a tradition for the UNESCO organization to hold scientific conferences on its popularization. The importance of pedagogical technology in increasing the country's spiritual and economic potential and improving education is being scientifically proven.

Also, the task of building a democratic, humane, legal society is entrusted to the growing young generation. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", as well as a number of works and speeches of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, set the goals and tasks of establishing education in the independent republic.

Education is a pedagogical process organized for purposeful improvement of the personality, which allows regular and systematic influence on the personality of the student.

According to the idea of the pedagogical technology theory of education, now the student is not only an object of the educational process, but also acts as a subject. Therefore, it is necessary for the teacher to take into account the internal capabilities of the student, external influences and sources of information. If this requirement is forgotten, it will be difficult to educate a person or all efforts will be ineffective.

It has the character of personality formation, management, and control, and the tasks defined in this regard should be solved not by random actions, but on the basis of pre-determined and carefully thought-out plans. In the process of education, its purpose, forms and methods, aspects of self-education and re-education of a person are important. The content of education is determined on the basis of social orders, and certain conditions are required for its implementation.

At the same time, in the process of educating the young generation in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan, the following recommendations and future tasks are of great importance:

- it is necessary to pay serious attention to this process in educational institutions with a

deep understanding of the newly introduced educational science, its purpose and its importance;

- it is necessary to prepare young people for social life, instill in them a broad worldview, a purposeful approach to their personal life, a sense of unity of plan and action;
- it is necessary to educate students about the essence of national and universal human values, to educate young people with deep knowledge and thinking, to enrich their minds;
- to understand the essence of universal moral standards (humanity, humility, mutual help, love, kindness, support of justice, humanitarianism, hatred of immorality, etc.)
- inculcating in pupils a sense of respect for legal and moral standards and a sense of citizenship, responsibility for social duty;
- formation of responsibility for nature protection, creation of ecological balance;
- forming a sense of patriotism and internationalism, establishing a sense of respect for other nations and peoples, not to belittle their rights and duties;
- it is necessary to teach people to value a person as a supreme value, to respect his honor, dignity, value, rights and duties.

After all, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev rightly noted, "... Today, times are changing rapidly. Young people are the ones who feel these changes the most. Let the youth be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time, he should not forget his identity. Let the call of who we are and the descendants of great people always resonate in their hearts and encourage them to stay true to themselves. How can we achieve this? Education, education and only education."

There are well-defined laws of the content of education, which have been improved over the centuries in accordance with the requirements of each era. The content of education includes the knowledge, skills and abilities, personal behavior and moral qualities that should be mastered by the child according to the educational goals and tasks determined by the child's age and social background.

In addition to informal leaders, the community of educators includes formal, educator-appointed leaders. Usually, formal leaders are made up of students who study with excellent grades and actively participate in team work, while informal leaders, although they do not display such qualities, follow their peers according to some of their qualities. The spiritual and moral image of informal leaders has a serious impact on other students. Therefore, together with the head of the class, the pedagogical team of the educational institution should identify informal leaders and directly monitor their activities.

The teacher's theoretical and practical understanding of the interrelationship and interdependence of all the elements of educational activity gives an opportunity to correctly direct the educational process. In this, special attention is paid to the activities and results, components of educational technologies that reveal the forms, methods, methods and tools of educational interaction in pedagogy, and the results and components of educational technologies.

Nowadays, perfect people who have acquired the latest and highest knowledge, skills and qualifications are playing an important decisive role in the development of the state and society.

By providing the current educational system with modern pedagogical technologies, which is aimed at the comprehensive formation of the personality, we will raise a mature generation that meets the requirements of world standards and grows up with a sense of belonging to the interests of the state and the people.

The system of retraining public education workers, who rely on the principles of mutual respect and trust, like all educational institutions of our republic, and the system of improving their qualifications, organizing classes through the use of modern pedagogical technologies, which are constantly being updated in the educational process, is becoming important in the era when the pace of life has accelerated to an incomparable level.

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